

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *The professional competence of a teacher is a set of professional and personal qualities necessary for successful activity, the ability to competently solve pedagogical problems in the process of educational, cognitive, educational and other activities together with students and for students.*

Key words: *professional competence, teacher, component, thinking, work, task, conditions, result.*

Professional competence of a teacher is a set of professional and personal qualities necessary for successful activity, the ability to professionally solve pedagogical tasks in the process of educational, cognitive, educational and other activities together with students and for students.

By analogy with the spheres of professional activity, two spheres can also be distinguished in the model of professional competence – motivational and operational. At the same time, the motivational sphere develops more effectively, the more actively the operational sphere of professional competence is formed and vice versa. Both spheres are interdependent. Nevertheless, if a person does not understand or poorly represents the real content of the work, the content of the profession, then it is impossible to form motivation for this activity, and even more so professional competence. Therefore, this article analyzes the operational sphere of activity and examines the components of the operational sphere of professional competence. Professional self-awareness is considered as the most important component of the operational sphere, which allows a person to operate with images of professional activity in its implementation. Professional self-awareness is based on the general self-awareness of the individual. Professional self-awareness is a complex of a person's ideas about himself as a professional, it is a holistic image of himself as a professional, as well as a person's idea of his behavior in the system of industrial relations and psychological attitudes towards himself as a professional.

According to experts, professional self-awareness includes: 1) a person's awareness of the norms, rules, models of his profession as standards for realizing his qualities. Here the foundations of a professional worldview are laid, later – a personal professional credo, a personal concept of professional work, from which a specialist will proceed in his work, which is extremely important for the formation of professional competence; 2) awareness of these qualities in other people, comparing oneself with some abstract or concrete colleague; 3) taking into account the assessment of oneself as a professional with colleagues' sides; 4) a person's self-assessment of their individual sides - understanding of themselves, their professional behavior, as well as emotional attitude and self-assessment. Professional self-awareness is based on professional self-esteem - retrospective ("I'm like a professional yesterday"), relevant ("I'm like a professional today"), potential ("I'm like a professional tomorrow"), ideal ("I'm like a professional in the distant future"). Professional self-assessment is a tool for the development of personal motivations and professional competence. 5) a positive assessment of oneself as a whole, the definition of one's positive qualities, prospects,

which leads to a positive Self–concept. A professional with such a level of self-awareness increases self-confidence, satisfaction with his profession, work efficiency, and the desire for self-realization increases [1, p. 44]. In the process of professionalization, as professionalism grows, professional self-awareness also changes. Thus, it expands by including new features of a developing profession, which imposes new requirements on a professional person; the criteria for evaluating oneself as a professional change when a person raises the bar higher when assessing their professional capabilities, i.e. the process of forming professional competence is carried out. Another component of the operational sphere is professional thinking, which consists in the use of mental operations as a means of carrying out professional activities. The professional type (warehouse) of thinking is the predominant use of techniques adopted specifically in this professional field for solving problematic problems, methods of analyzing professional situations, making professional decisions, methods of scooping out the content of the subject of labor. Professional tasks often have incomplete data, lack of information, because professional situations change quickly. The development of professional thinking is an important aspect of the process of professionalization of a person and a prerequisite for the success of professional activity. Professional competence is associated with developed professional thinking. Professional thinking includes the process of generalized and indirect reflection of professional reality by a person (the subject of work, tasks, conditions and results of work); ways for a person to gain new knowledge about different aspects of work and ways of their transformation; techniques for setting, formulating and solving professional tasks; stages of decision-making and implementation in professional activity; methods of goal formation and plan formation in the course of work, the development of new strategies for professional activity. All types of thinking (theoretical, practical, reproductive, creative, visual-figurative, verbal-logical, visual-effective, analytical, intuitive) ensure the quality of professional thinking, they act as its characteristics. The improvement of professional thinking may consist, on the one hand, in its specification, and on the other – in leaving the profession into a broader life context, as well as in increasing integrity, flexibility, etc. A sign of new professional thinking is called attention to alternative points of view, dialogicity, pluralism, strengthening the role of not only external, but also internal, "thinking" technologies. The operational sphere of professional activity in today's rapidly changing working conditions often requires the deployment of creative professional thinking. Professional creativity is finding new non–standard ways of solving professional problems, analyzing professional situations, making professional decisions [2, p. 78]. The results of professional creativity can be: a new understanding of the subject of work (new ideas, laws, concepts, principles, paradigms), a new approach to the methods of professional actions with the subject of work (new models, new technologies, rules), orientation to obtain fundamentally new results, attracting new groups of consumers of their product. Professional creativity requires the development of a number of new qualities in a person:

- the need for a new idea;
- seeing a problem where other people don't see it yet;
- the ability to notice alternatives, to see the subject of work from a completely new side;
- ability to switch quickly and overcome barriers;
- the ability to subjectively assimilate – to mentally include oneself in the system of objects and means of labor;
- the ability to pay attention to unusual, sometimes seemingly insignificant events;

- willingness to be critical of established generally accepted truths and new ideas;
- the ability to create new combinations from known combinations, to carry out all these mental transformations in relation to different aspects of work – the subject, the means, the result;
- willingness to work with a new, for example, computer reality. To characterize the operational sphere, professional learnability is also important – openness to further professional development, readiness to master new means of labor, professional knowledge and skills, active adaptation of a person to the updated conditions of professional experience. Professional self-awareness, thinking and learning ability are the basis for the formation of professional competence, which acts as a characteristic of professional maturity of the individual.

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